

Big Stuff Conference 2019

Heritage and Areas of Innovation

How to conserve and develop industrial heritage sites as sites of *heritage and innovation*?

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Most industrial heritage sites were historically places of innovation, and most such sites relate to urban and regional development that is innovation-orientated. Thus, linking conservation and innovation might be advantageous for heritage sites. So-called areas of innovation are—in short—not only part of urban development, but also actively managed in the sense used by the International Association of Science Parks and Areas of Innovation (IASP). Heritage sites require management; but their status demands a focus on heritage conservation and careful development—especially for UNESCO World Heritage sites. Understanding industrial heritage as *sites of heritage and innovation* leads to the question: What can we learn from managing industrial heritage sites in ways that satisfy conservation requirements while also aiming to foster innovation?

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UNESCO World Heritage Zollverein, Essen © Oevermann 2015

Euratechnologies, Lille © Oevermann 2019

Grünerløkka, Oslo, © Oevermann 2017

Lapadu, Duisburg © Oevermann 2007

Workshop at Svetovar, Pilzen © Oevermann 2013

This conference contribution is based mainly on two outputs from long-term research process with two projects on the transformation of industrial heritage sites: Firstly, we sought to understand conflicting and “bridging” values in order to balance the different demands of conservation and development (Oevermann & Mieg 2015). The project analysed differing perspectives on the transformational processes of various European industrial heritage sites. Secondly, we employed a holistic approach, bringing together eight criteria of good practice in conservation and development (<http://good-practice.indumap.de/home/>). The research project on good practice considered the policies and guidelines of TICCIH, ICOMOS and UNESCO, and followed the recommendations of Birgitta Ringbeck concerning the management of UNESCO heritage sites (Ringbeck 2008).

Areas of innovation

The International Association of Science Parks and Areas of Innovation is a global network of professionals managing science parks and areas of innovation. In brief, they define areas of innovation as hybrid spaces: "Areas of innovation are places designed and curated to attract entrepreneurial-minded people, skilled talent, knowledge-intensive businesses and investments, by developing and combining a set of infrastructural, institutional, scientific, technological, educational and social assets, together with value added services, thus enhancing sustainable economic development and prosperity with and for the community. There are many different models of areas of innovation — *spanning from the broader city or region model with innovation activities in different locations within the area, to more place-specific projects like innovation districts, knowledge quarters, science parks, innovation hubs and the like. As a common feature they all have a management team tasked to execute a strategy conducive to growing innovation activity in the area.*" (italics added, IASP 2019)

The phrase “areas of innovation” is the latest terminology for quite a range of upcoming concepts. In the 1970s, technology parks attracted and managed development at specific locations, which were often poorly embedded within wider urban and regional planning frameworks; business incubation centres followed. Both concepts lacked integration with science, one of several increasingly important impulses for development in knowledge societies; consequently, science and technology parks replaced the former concepts. Today, it is obvious that the development of specific, often large, sites is relevant for urban and regional development. Furthermore, the more recent ideas concerning temporary uses, the growing creative industries, and the importance of heritage sites were difficult to incorporate within the framework of science and technology parks, and so the IASP started using the concept of areas of innovation (Mieg 2019).

To date, there is twenty years of professional experience of managing areas of innovation, and the IASP is active in organising discussion on this theme (e.g. a yearly conference), including exchange of professional advice and guidance on good practice. Rowe (2014) formulates nine categories of good practice; in summary (Mieg et al. forthcoming), these are:

1. Set out a strategy and objectives
2. Initiate and strengthen the engagement of the knowledge base (e.g., universities)
3. Interact with the public sector
4. Secure and attract land, capital and revenue
5. Use and empower the local skill base
6. Address regional/national markets
7. Provide key services to tenants
8. Implement a model for development
9. Select strong leadership, based on board and/or committee structures

Industrial heritage conservation and innovation

Heritage conservation and innovation are two perspectives (from a more theoretical point of view, termed discourses) that differ but are both relevant in urban planning. The contrast becomes obvious when considering innovation as taking risks (Mieg 2012), whereas heritage conservation focusses on continuous and careful protection and preservation. However, discourses and practice show that both conservation and innovation are discussed and implemented in the same field of industrial heritage sites.

The following three examples introduce approaches that relate heritage conservation and innovation; obviously, there are more cases to identify and discuss. This short overview is based on the projects' own literature, and lacks additional critical analysis based on primary empirical research and evidence. Furthermore, it should be noted that the projects themselves were not connected to the concept of areas of innovation, whereas I contrast them with the categories proposed by Rowe (good practice on managing areas of innovation) to obtain an (explorative) understanding of whether—and how—heritage and innovation are brought together in the field.

The joint Initiative *InduCult 2.0* addresses industrial heritage and the present and future potentials of industrial culture. It focusses on more peripheral and/or rural areas of Europe with an industrial past. Here, industrial culture is understood as a characteristic of identity; in reviving pioneering spirit; as an attractor of new labour force and youth; for improving image; as well as a means to combine traditional production with innovativeness or creativity (Görmar et al. 2019, 32f). Thus, industrial culture is the main feature of the strategy for conserving and developing industrial heritage, and defines their objectives. Mostly “*the often attractive assets of (old) industrial sites* [are used] for establishing creative and cultural centres as well as measures fostering innovation, entrepreneurship and local value chains in an industry-based setting” (italics added, Görmar et al. 2019, 44). Furthermore, the project documentation shows that cooperation, collaborations, and networks (especially those between creatives and industries), available workspace and innovative financial incentives are as important as the conservation and use of tangible heritage assets for initiating and

supporting a creative environment (Görmar et al. 2019, 45). The project agrees on the importance of three categories proposed by Rowe (2014): (1) to set out a strategy and objectives; (5) use and empower the local skill base; and probably (6) addresses regional markets.

The Shift-X project is also a European joint project that focuses on old industrial regions, heritage conservation and present and future development. Similarly to InduCult 2.0, the central idea is the valorisation of industrial culture. Here one of the three key areas concerns innovating heritage-based products (Shift-X 2019). The project aims are: to set up action plans for innovation in traditional products (comprising crafts products and visitor activities), as well as to implement management concepts for tandem transfer and institutions engaged in industrial heritage. As with InduCult, Shift-X also set up: (1) strategies and objectives. Three—often interdependent—methods for innovation were used: design-led method, improved story-telling and improved marketing. Whereas the last two methods are familiar, the first might need some explanation. Design-led methods: “thereby actively include designers who utilise traditional, heritage-based elements in new ways and search for connections to active industries and marketing via fairs and exhibitions. It relies on the combination of designers and creative industries, along with traditional crafts and products.” (Harfst / Fischer 2014, 8) Here, the following categories are addressed: (5) the use and empowerment of the local skill base, and (7) the provision of (key) services to tenants are obvious, and there are possible links to (6) addressing regional markets.

Especially interesting is that the management compendium of the project formulates the following success factors: strong political leadership; cooperation with powerful economic partners; and the involvement of locals, grassroots initiatives and communities (Albrecht / Walther 2014, 54–64). These recommendations overlap with categories: (3) to interact with the public sector, (8) to implement a model for development and (9) to select strong leadership based on board and/or committee structures. However, it does not clearly address point (2) to initiate and strengthen the engagement of the (scientific) knowledge base (e.g., universities).

The third example is the network project Vogtlandpioniere, which is part of the German national programme We! Change through innovation in the region (Wir! Wandel durch Innovation in der Region). The project understands the culture of built environment (Baukultur) as a trigger for conservation, innovation and cooperation, aiming at fostering development. Here, as in the InduCult 2.0 project, reviving the pioneering spirit of former times is addressed as an objective. Where this project differs is in its approach that innovative ideas and new innovative technologies enable the rediscovery and conservation of the industrial heritage and historic environment, and at the same time the task of conserving this built heritage generates innovative ideas and new technologies (Vogtlandpioniere 2019). The projects started in summer 2019, therefore no results are available yet. The project setting fulfils most of the categories proposed by Rowe, and seems to follow a promising task. The establishment of a competence centre, in particular, which will continue after the project phase, might serve the ongoing objectives: (4) securing revenue, (5) empowering the local skill base, as well as (7) providing key services.

All projects face the challenge that certain categories might only be included in the management approach during the pilot project period. In particular, parameters (2) to initiate and strengthen the engagement of the knowledge base (e.g., universities), (7) to provide key services to tenants, and (9) strong leadership, might weaken or be lost after this initial phase.

Table 1 summarises which of the projects match the categories proposed by Rowe. Some projects meet only limited categories. In these cases the focus is listed (e.g., category: to interact with the public sector; Shift-X project: to interact with communities).

	Categories (from Rowe)	InduCult 2.0	Shift-X	Vogtlandpioniere
1	Strategy and objectives	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Scientific knowledge base	During project	During project	During project
3	Public sector	No	Communities	Yes
4	Land, capital, revenue	Non-specific	Non-specific	Through competence centre
5	Use and empower the local skill base	During project / through cooperation	During project / through cooperation	Through competence centre / cooperation
6	Regional/national markets	Regional	Regional	Regional
7	Key services	Non-specific (During project)	e.g., methods for innovation	Cooperation and competence centre
8	Development model	Non-specific	Yes	Yes
9	Leadership	Non-specific (During project)	Issue addressed	Open

Good practice categories (from Rowe) implemented by the three example projects

As mentioned, the three projects were not oriented towards areas of innovation; presumably they were not aware of it. Nevertheless, the short comparison shows, firstly, that heritage and innovation are both addressed in professional practice. In the field of industrial heritage sites, the example projects display their focus on this combination, which seems to enable heritage conservation through innovative approaches that (re)use the tangible (e.g., buildings) and intangible (e.g., pioneering spirit) local heritage. Secondly, the categories of good practice for managing areas of innovation are already (partly) applied to managing industrial heritage sites, although not explicitly. That situation makes a systematic implementation even more promising. Therefore, it is useful to analyse in more detail how heritage sites can learn from areas of innovation.

The knowledge-transfer project

The forthcoming project, “Areas of Innovation for Industrial Heritage Sites”, applies research knowledge to the practice of heritage management at the Zollverein Industrial Complex in Germany, a former coal mine and coking plant that is now a UNESCO World Heritage site. Zollverein represents a complete example of coal mining infrastructure, providing evidence of the 150-year evolution and decline of an industry that was essential to the Ruhr region.

The project suggests two work packages: The first package develops a monitoring system that guides heritage conservation and includes the development aims of the site, e.g., Zollverein as location of design; Zollverein and the cradle-to-cradle principle; Zollverein and neighbourhood development; and Zollverein and regional cultural tourism, etc. Here, the vision for Zollverein understands the heritage sector as a growing industry, including innovation processes. The challenge is how to trigger innovation through heritage conservation. Secondly, we use the concept of industrial culture (Industriekultur) to connect the industrial past with the present and future as an area of innovation. Additionally, the concept of industrial culture enables Zollverein to contribute to the discourse on industrial futures in so-called ‘post’-industrial countries.

Prozess of the Knowledge-Transfer Project © Mieg, 2019

The practical task is: How can heritage management be controlled and monitored when taking into account urban innovation processes in the urban environment? As is customary in urban development planning and in the aforementioned project, the working process will comprise a series of themed workshops. The aim is to support the monitoring of Zollverein in the following areas in a generic sense, so that the monitoring approach can also be adapted to other World Heritage sites. For the process design, experience from sustainable urban development can be used (Mieg 2012), namely the Local Action Plan. These plans include contributions from various actors (local, as well as World Heritage Centre, WHC) that are translated into guidance and criteria/indicators for monitoring. In our case the Local Action Plan is not primarily aligned to climate or sustainability goals

(as it is common), but instead to the site's OUV (Outstanding Universal Value) and to achieving balanced development compatible with historical monuments. Figure 1 outlines the process of the knowledge-transfer project.

The process needs to clarify these questions:

- Actors: Which are the relevant actors to contribute to the Local Action Plan?
- Continuity: How to perpetuate initial processes and how to continuously implement the results of the project?
- General vs. specific: How to integrate the specific criteria and indicators, that are important as each heritage site is specific into a monitoring system, which is general otherwise it cannot be supervised by WHC/UNESCO?

The product of the requested knowledge transfer is a simple monitoring and decision-support tool, i.e., a web-based program (open source) that brings together the responsible actors and supports decisions for monitoring. This program for monitoring the decision-making process is intended to support the generic Local Action Plan

The expected lessons from areas of innovation

First of all, industrial heritage sites need an explicit and active management (strategy, objectives, plan, team) that is continuously checked and adapted. It is challenging to maintain the balance between long-term conservation and short- and mid-term innovations, as well as to adapt to dynamic processes of upcoming needs and interests (e.g., those defined by the users). Therefore, this requires a dedicated team to work full-time on such tasks. In particular, discontinuities following project periods—be they similar to the introduced examples funded by programmes (EU or national funds) or be they local action plans as suggested in the knowledge-transfer project—need to be bridged and successful processes have to be secured.

Furthermore, appropriate definition and implementation of strategies, objectives and management models are needed. This task requires local organisation, as the various actors from politics and planning, possible cooperation partners, and others, should be integrated. Endogenetic development processes and participation are empowered only together with local actors. Finally, the management process requires professional exchange and guidance—not only to guarantee continuous checks and balances of the strategies, objectives and management model worked out during the process of interaction with partners, politics and planners—but also to gain a better understanding of the specifics of the site and its management tasks. Through discussion and comparison within an international network. Furthermore, the responsible actors also gain a better understanding of the singular local and specific aspects of their heritage site and the management of which requires unique solutions that are generated locally.

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